

Project: 101207598 –2024 MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowship Program

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D1.1– MOBILITY DECLARATION, PROJECT MANAGEMENT & RISK MITIGATION PLAN & DATA MITIGATION PLAN

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Author	Keyvan Aghababaiyan
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1 INTRODUCTION

This project management handbook summarizes the key elements involved in organizing and coordinating the project. It outlines the overall structure, covering work packages, deliverables, and milestones, describes the core management procedures to be followed, and details the communication pathways and activities that will support implementation throughout the project. The handbook also documents the researcher's mobility status, confirming full compliance with the MSCA mobility rule, an essential requirement for the eligibility of the Deterministic6G-V2X fellowship. As a dynamic document, the handbook may be updated during the project lifecycle whenever adjustments are required to address emerging needs or changes in project execution.

2 MOBILITY AND ELIGIBILITY OF THE RESEARCHER

In accordance with the MSCA mobility rule, Dr. Keyvan Aghababaiyan fully meets the eligibility requirements for the Deterministic6G-V2X MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowship. During the five years preceding the call deadline, the researcher's main place of residence and professional activity has been outside Spain. Specifically, from 11/09/2019 to 23/01/2024 (1596 days), Dr. Aghababaiyan resided and worked in Iran, where he held a postdoctoral research position at the University of Tehran and collaborated with several research groups and technology companies. He joined Spain only recently, from 24/01/2024 to 11/09/2024 (232 days), to work as a Senior Postdoctoral Researcher in the European 6G-SHINE project at the UWICORE laboratory (UMH).

The researcher's mobility record demonstrates continuous full-time research activity outside Spain for the vast majority of the 5-year reference period. His total presence in Spain before the call deadline remained well below the 12-month limit required by the MSCA PF mobility condition. Therefore, Dr. Aghababaiyan fully satisfies the MSCA eligibility criteria while bringing significant international experience from Iran and prior involvement in an EU-funded 6G research environment.

3 PROJECT OVERVIEW

The Deterministic6G-V2X project is a two-year initiative supported by the European Commission through the Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Postdoctoral Fellowships program. According to the grant agreement, the Universidad Miguel Hernández (UMH) in Elche, Spain, serves as the coordinating institution. The research activities will be conducted by Dr. Keyvan Aghababaiyan (the researcher) at the UWICORE laboratory of UMH, under the supervision of Prof. Javier Gozalvez.

3.1 RESEARCHER INFORMATION

Keyvan Aghababaiyan is an MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow and postdoctoral researcher at the Universidad Miguel Hernández (UMH) in Elche, Spain, contributing to the 6G-Shine project and leading the development of the Deterministic6G-V2X research program. His work at UMH focuses on deterministic communication-computing-control co-design for next-generation 6G vehicular systems, integrating AI-driven scheduling, stochastic modelling, and real-time network analysis. Before joining UMH, he held a prestigious postdoctoral fellowship at the University of Tehran, funded by the Iranian

National Elite Foundation, where he worked on nanoscale, molecular, and neuro-spike communication systems. He received his PhD in Telecommunication Engineering from the University of Tehran with the highest distinction (Excellent), following an MSc from Sharif University of Technology and dual BSc degrees in Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering from Amirkabir University of Technology, where he ranked 1st among all Electrical Engineering students. Earlier, he placed 340th out of more than 400,000 applicants (top 0.08%) in the national university entrance exam, reflecting exceptional academic performance from the outset of his career. His research focuses on 6G wireless systems, V2X communications, stochastic modelling, AI-assisted signal processing, and nanoscale/neuro-inspired communication.

He has published extensively in leading IEEE journals, including IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Transactions on Communications, IEEE Communications Letters, and IEEE Transactions on Nanobioscience. He also serves as a reviewer for 25 high-impact journals such as IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology, IEEE Transactions on Communications, IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Wireless Communications Letters, and several IET and Elsevier journals. His scientific career has been recognized through multiple elite scholarships, two consecutive Best PhD Student Awards, and a full postdoctoral fellowship from the Iranian National Elite Foundation. Keyvan Aghababaiyan brings a strong interdisciplinary background that directly supports the development of deterministic communication–computing–control frameworks for future 6G V2X systems.

3.2 SUPERVISOR INFORMATION

Javier Gozalvez is a Full Professor at UMH and serves as the director of the UWICORE laboratory, where he leads research in Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM), V2X communications, and next-generation 5G and 6G networking technologies, as well as topics related to industry 5.0. He is widely acknowledged internationally for his scientific contributions, with a publication record exceeding 120 works and more than 9,700 citations. His technical leadership is reflected in his role as principal investigator at UMH in 6 European research projects, including Horizon Europe initiatives such as 6G-SHINE, RE4DY, and Zero-SWARM, along with 17 national projects, 18 regional initiatives, and 31 industry-funded R&D contracts.

His collaborative network includes leading institutions such as King's College London (UK), the Italian National Research Council (CNR), and the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (Germany). Prof. Gozalvez previously served as Editor-in-Chief of IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine (a Q1 JCR journal in the CAM domain), and President of the IEEE Vehicular Technology Society (VTS), and continues to be a member of its Board of Governors. Over the past decade, he has supervised more than 13 doctoral candidates and over 20 R&D engineers, and he currently supervises 5 postdoctoral researchers. Many of his former trained researchers now hold prominent positions across Europe, including, for example, the European V2X technical lead at Hyundai in Germany.

4 PROJECT STRUCTURE

The structure and scheduling of the Deterministic6G-V2X project are presented in the Gantt chart in Table 4.1. This table outlines the planned activities and timeline as defined in the grant agreement,

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covering all scientific, training, and management tasks. The distribution of effort across the Work Packages (WPs) has been designed to maintain a balanced progression between research activities, supervision and training, and administrative duties. The timing of each deliverable and milestone has been strategically organized to support continuous monitoring of the project’s advancement and to ensure the timely completion of all objectives.

Table 4.1. Gantt chart of the project, including Milestones (MS) and Deliverables (D).

Month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	
WP1	D1.1		D1.1																	D1.1					
WP2	Phase 1					D2.1						D2.2			D2.2						D2.1	Phase 2			
WP3										D3.1					D3.1						D3.2				D3.2
WP4			D4.1																	D4.1					
WP5												D5.1								D5.1					
MSs	MS1		MS2												MS3,4					MS5	MS6			MS7	

4.1 WORK PACKAGES

The work plan of the Deterministic6G-V2X project is organized into five Work Packages, as summarized in Table 4.2. The non-technical components include project management (WP1), training and knowledge transfer (WP4), and dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities (WP5). The scientific tasks are grouped into two tightly connected technical WPs: WP2 develops stochastic models for deterministic communication–computing–control co-design, while WP3 builds upon these models to design elastic and predictive scheduling frameworks for 6G-enabled V2X systems. The modelling foundations established in WP2 directly support the scheduling and co-design strategies addressed in WP3, while the results of WP3 provide performance indicators to refine and validate the stochastic models. As indicated in Table 4.1, both technical WPs follow a two-phase structure, ensuring that complexity is managed progressively and that the execution of the project proceeds smoothly from data-driven co-design (Phase 1) to predictive AI-driven techniques (Phase 2).

Table 4.2. List of WPs.

WP	WP Title	Duration	PMs
WP1	Project management	M1-M24	2
WP2	Stochastic models for communication, computing, and control co-design	M1-M21	7
WP3	Communication, computing, and control co-design	M4-M24	9
WP4	Training and transfer of knowledge	M1-M24	4
WP5	Dissemination, exploitation, and communication	M1-M24	2

4.2 DELIVERABLES

Deliverables serve as key instruments for tracking the progress of Deterministic6G-V2X and documenting the implementation and main results of each Work Package. Every WP is linked to one or more deliverables, and the project includes the full set defined in the grant agreement (see Table 4.3). These deliverables cover both technical and non-technical outputs, ensuring a comprehensive reporting of scientific advances, training activities, management procedures, and dissemination efforts.

The technical deliverables associated with WP2 and WP3 (D2.x and D3.x) will be updated across the two project phases to reflect the incremental development of stochastic models and co-design frameworks. This phased updating guarantees that the deliverables offer an accurate, up-to-date representation of the project’s technological evolution. Non-technical deliverables from WP1, WP4, and WP5 provide structured reporting on management, training, knowledge transfer, and dissemination, ensuring continuous and transparent monitoring throughout the project duration. All deliverables marked as “PU” will be publicly released on the project website.

Table 4.3. List of deliverables.

ID	Deliverable Name	WP	Level	Deadline
D1.1	Mobility Declaration, Project Management & Risk Mitigation Plan	WP1	PU	M1(1st)/M3(2nd)/M20 (3th)
D2.1	Stochastic models for communication–computing–control co-design	WP2	PU	M6 (1st) / M21 (2nd)
D2.2	CAM scenarios and generated datasets	WP2	PU	M12 (1st) / M15 (2nd)
D3.1	Communication–computing–control co-design	WP3	PU	M10 (1st) / M15 (2nd)
D3.2	Predictive communication–computing–control co-design	WP3	PU	M21 (1st) / M24 (2nd)
D4.1	Training program, career development plan, and evaluation questionnaire	WP4	SEN	M3 (1st) / M19 (2nd)
D5.1	Plan for dissemination, exploitation, and communication	WP5	PU	M12 (1st) / M20 (2nd)

4.3 MILESTONES

The Deterministic6G-V2X project comprises eight milestones in total. The non-technical milestones (MS1, MS2, MS5) serve to confirm the proper execution of management, communication, dissemination, exploitation, and training activities, as well as the timely fulfillment of reporting obligations. The technical milestones (MS3, MS4, MS6, MS7, MS8) are intended to track the scientific progress of the project and assess whether the technical objectives defined in the grant agreement are being achieved.

Verification of each milestone is ensured through the preparation of the corresponding deliverables (see Table 4.3) and through the open availability of the project’s main outputs, including code and

datasets generated across WP2 and WP3. A consolidated overview of all milestones is provided in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4. List of milestones.

ID	Milestone description	WPs	Month	Verifiability
MS1	Project kick-off and website launch.	WP1	M1	Deliverables (Deliv.)
MS2	Initial deliverables completed and training program.	WP1,4	M3	Deliv.
MS3	CAM scenarios, and datasets.	WP2	M15	Deliv. & Datasets
MS4	Communication, computing, and control co-design.	WP3	M15	Report & Deliv. & code
MS5	Dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan ready and revised.	WP5	M20	Deliv.
MS6	Stochastic models.	WP2	M21	Deliv.
MS7	Predictive communication, computing, and control co-design.	WP3	M24	Report & Deliv. & code

5 PROJECT MANAGEMENT

The overall management of Deterministic6G-V2X, including financial oversight and administrative coordination, will be carried out by the researcher, with continuous support from the supervisor and the EU projects office and administrative units of the host institution.

5.1 PROJECT REPORTING

Project reporting for Deterministic6G-V2X will be carried out by the researcher and is structured around three core components: timesheet documentation, internal monitoring meetings, and the preparation of project deliverables. Each month, the researcher will complete timesheets detailing the hours allocated to each Work Package (WP). These timesheets will be submitted to the host institution's administrative office and shared with the supervisor.

To ensure continuous oversight, the researcher will hold bi-weekly meetings with the supervisor to review scientific progress and to evaluate the status of non-technical activities, including dissemination, communication, and training. In addition, project reporting will be formalized through the deliverables outlined in Section 3.2. All deliverables will be drafted by the researcher and subsequently reviewed by the supervisor prior to their public release.

5.2 OPEN ACCESS

Both the supervisor and the researcher have an established history of releasing open-source software, datasets, and preprints. Building on this shared commitment, the Deterministic6G-V2X project will adopt a comprehensive set of open-science practices:

- **Early and open access to scientific publications:** The project will ensure that all scientific outputs are made available as early as possible through open repositories such as arXiv and Zenodo. Whenever suitable, journal submissions will target high-impact venues offering gold open-access options to maximize the visibility and accessibility of the research.
- **Research data management aligned with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable):** All datasets, code, and models produced during the project will be publicly released on Zenodo at the time of the related preprint’s publication (Accessibility). Zenodo will assign a DOI to each output, ensuring Findability. Comprehensive deliverables and technical documentation will accompany all releases and will be made available both on Zenodo and the project website to support re-use and integration by the research community (Interoperability). All materials will be distributed under a CC BY, or equivalent, license to guarantee Reusability.
- **Reproducibility of research outputs:** Every scientific publication will include the necessary methodological information, design assumptions, simulation parameters, tested scenarios, analytical tools, and AI components, to allow independent validation of the project’s findings. Extended methodological details will also be documented in project deliverables and published on the project website, ensuring full reproducibility despite the page-length limitations imposed by many journals.

5.3 RISK MANAGEMENT

The objective of the project’s risk management procedure is to reduce the likelihood that internal or external factors disrupt or delay the execution of Deterministic6G-V2X, thereby safeguarding the technical progress and overall quality of implementation. Table 5.1 summarizes the scientific and non-scientific risks identified for the project, indicating the associated Work Packages, the proposed mitigation strategies, and the assessed Severity (S) and Likelihood (L) of each risk. These risks will be actively monitored throughout the entire project duration, with regular reviews led by the researcher. Additional risks, and corresponding mitigation measures will be incorporated as necessary to ensure continuous and proactive management.

Table 5.1. Critical implementation risks and corresponding mitigation measures.

Description	Proposed risk-mitigation measures	WP
Stochastic models complexity. S: Med. L: Med.	Model derivation can be complex. The researcher and supervisor (R&S) have a strong mathematical background and extensive analytical expertise. If complexity becomes intractable, we will apply reasonable assumptions and partial numerical methods.	WP2
Challenge in joint scheduling. S: Med. L: High.	If complexity hinders closed-form solutions for co-design (WP3), we will simplify with adjustments while maintaining deterministic principles. Offline AI will be explored for predictive co-design if real-time is challenging (WP2-3).	WP2-3
Datasets for predictive co-design. S: Med. L: Low.	AI-based predictive co-design requires comprehensive datasets that may be unavailable in the community. We will progressively generate these datasets with varying granularity to ensure timely availability and support project progress.	WP2-3

Simulation cluster limitations. S: High. L: Low.	WP2-3 is simulation-intensive and requires AI-processing capabilities (GPUs). The UWICORE lab has its own simulation cluster (400 CPUs, 900 GB RAM, 8 GPUs). In case of Failure or congestion, the researcher will use UMH’s simulation cluster.	WP2-3
CAM simulator is not ready. S: High. L: Low.	The host lab already has a working version of the simulator that bridges AUTOWARE, CARLA, and V2X communication models. Two researchers and a technician are available to integrate additional functionalities as needed to meet project requirements.	WP2-3
Training program not adequate. S: Med. L: Low.	UMH has organized 3 editions of the Conoce TP and is committed to future editions or alternatives as part of its EU HRS4R and HR Excellence Award commitment. UMH will also offer relevant TPs regularly organized by RUVID.	WP4
WPs KPIs cannot be met. S: Low. L: Med.	KPIs are set based on previous R&S performance and Deterministic6G-V2X potential. The dissemination plan identifies alternative journals if initial submissions aren’t accepted. R&S will continue working on publications after the project concludes.	WP5

5.4 MANAGEMENT OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY (IPR)

The researcher and the supervisor maintain a strong commitment to open science and to the unrestricted dissemination of the project’s outcomes. Accordingly, no Intellectual Property (IP) barriers are anticipated during the execution of Deterministic6G-V2X. Should an unexpected result arise that warrants IP protection, the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) office of the host institution will provide the necessary guidance, and the project’s dissemination plan will be adjusted to ensure proper handling of the protected material.

5.5 ACKNOWLEDGEMENT OF FUNDING

All materials produced or disseminated as part of the project’s communication, exploitation, and dissemination activities, including deliverables, presentations, scientific publications, software releases, and any other publicly shared outputs, will include the European Union emblem and the required funding acknowledgment. Figure 1 illustrates the standard acknowledgment format to be used.

Figure 1. Acknowledgment of funding.

Whenever appropriate, the following statement will also be included:

“This project has received funding from the European Union under the 2024 MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowship program (project no. 101207598).”

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6 COMMUNICATION

6.1 INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

Internal communication within Deterministic6G-V2X refers to the communications between the researcher, the supervisor, and the host institution. Regular interaction between the researcher and the supervisor will be maintained through bi-weekly technical meetings and ongoing email correspondence. Additional meetings will be arranged when required by the project's scientific or administrative needs. The researcher's office is in close proximity to the supervisor's workspace, which naturally facilitates informal technical discussions alongside the scheduled meetings. Communication with the administrative and EU-projects staff of the host institution will primarily take place via email, ensuring timely coordination of financial and administrative matters.

6.2 EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION

External communication encompasses all actions aimed at presenting and disseminating the project's objectives, activities, and results to a broad audience, including both technical stakeholders and the public. These activities will be carried out continuously throughout the duration of the project and will be documented in the relevant dissemination and communication deliverable (D5.1, see Table 4.3). The specific external communication measures planned for Deterministic6G-V2X are detailed in the following sections.

6.2.1 Website and social media

The project website will serve as the central platform for presenting the vision, objectives, and activities of Deterministic6G-V2X. It will be updated on a regular basis with news, intermediate and final results, deliverables, scientific publications, and presentation materials, including recorded talks. The website is intended to function as the most comprehensive and authoritative source of information on the project's progress and achievements. The project's website is available at [1]. Project updates will also be shared through the researcher's LinkedIn profile, with each post linking back to the project website to ensure consistency and visibility. To further increase outreach, these posts will be re-shared by the supervisor through his LinkedIn account, helping broaden the dissemination of project outcomes across professional networks.

6.2.2 Press and media coverage

The project plans to issue a minimum of two press releases. The first will be distributed at the start of the project to introduce the vision, objectives, and expected contributions of Deterministic6G-V2X. A second press release will be prepared at the project's conclusion to highlight the key scientific results and the overall impact achieved. With the support of the host institution's press office and RUVID, these press releases will be disseminated widely through regional and national media channels. The objective of these releases is to increase the project's visibility and to encourage broader communication through radio and television interviews at both local and national levels. Within the Valencian region,

dissemination will also be supported through institutional outlets such as the UMH Sapiens magazine and other UMH communication platforms.

6.2.3 Other communication activities

Additional communication activities will focus on public outreach and STEM promotion, particularly among young students. These actions aim to increase societal awareness of the relevance and impact of Deterministic6G-V2X. The project will seek participation in outreach initiatives organized by local institutions, such as the EU Researchers' Night MEDNIGHT GTS coordinated by the Valencian universities, as well as events hosted by the University Miguel Hernández, including the Elche/UMH Week of Science and the UMH Open Days.

7 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is a document outlining how the research data will be handled during the Deterministic6G-V2X project and after its completion. More precisely, the DMP describes the data management life cycle for all data sets that will be collected, processed, or generated by the project. It details what data will be collected, processed, or generated, the methodology and standards to be followed, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved. This DMP has been prepared following the template provided by the European Commission at [2].

8 DATA SUMMARY

The Deterministic6G-V2X project does not foresee the re-use of existing data. The accomplishment of the Deterministic6G-V2X project objectives, namely (i) stochastic modeling for communication, computing, and control co-design, (ii) elastic joint scheduling over the 6G-enabled Local-Edge-Cloud (LEC) continuum, and (iii) predictive AI-based co-design, heavily relies on the availability of Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) datasets, and, as of today, no CAM datasets have been publicly released. Nevertheless, the Deterministic6G-V2X project is committed to continuously monitoring research developments in this domain and is ready to consider the re-use of existing data as soon as suitable CAM datasets become openly available.

Table 8.1. Data summary.

WP	Data name	Data type	Description and format	Expected size
WP2	CAM dataset	Dataset	A CAM dataset contains the driving environment information collected by Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) through onboard sensors and Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communications.	10-100 GB
WP2	Stochastic end to end latency model for communication, computing, and control	Analytical model and software	Analytical stochastic end to end latency model capturing communication latencies, computing latency, jitter, burstiness, and	10 MB-20 MB

			resource availability in deterministic 6G-V2X systems.	
WP3	Deterministic 6G-V2X system-level simulator	Software	System-level simulator for evaluating joint communication, computing, and control co-design strategies and elastic scheduling mechanisms across the LEC continuum. Implementation in MATLAB or Python.	1–10 GB
WP2	Predictive AI models for resource orchestration	Software	AI-based predictive models (e.g., transformers, generative AI) to forecast task demand, contextual evolution, and resource usage patterns for proactive deterministic scheduling. Implementation in MATLAB or Python.	5–10 GB

CAM datasets are instrumental to the accomplishment of the three main objectives of the Deterministic6G-V2X project: (i) development of stochastic models for communication, computing, and control co-design, (ii) design of elastic and predictive joint scheduling strategies across the LEC continuum, and (iii) development of AI-based predictive frameworks for proactive orchestration.

In addition, each project objective is expected to generate data (datasets, analytical model, and software, see Table 8.1) that will be used both to verify the achievement of performance targets and to support intertwined objectives. For example, stochastic models developed under WP2 will feed the elastic scheduling framework of WP3. In the second phase of the project, predictive AI models will enhance both stochastic modeling accuracy and proactive scheduling decisions. All generated datasets and software will be openly released through the project’s Zenodo community and the project website in accordance with open science principles.

Beyond datasets and software, the project will generate scientific publications and public deliverables. All deliverables with public dissemination level will be openly released on Zenodo and on the project website. These deliverables will provide detailed documentation of methodology, validation, and results.

Scientific publications, primarily journal and conference papers, will disseminate the main technical outcomes of the Deterministic6G-V2X project. A preprint open-access version of each publication will be made publicly available on Zenodo and on the project website. The researcher will update the project website to reflect the new publication, deliverables, and dataset.

All data types identified in Table 8.1, along with deliverables and publications, will be generated and prepared by Dr. Keyvan Aghababaiyan during the execution of the Deterministic6G-V2X project. The resulting datasets, software, and publications will provide a solid foundation for future research on deterministic systems and benefit the broader V2X and CAM research community.

9 FAIR DATA

9.3 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

All data (datasets, software, deliverables, and publications) generated by the Deterministic6G-V2X project will be openly released on the Deterministic6G-V2X project Zenodo community. Through

Zenodo, all Deterministic6G-V2X project data will be assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) that allows the persistent identification of the released data.

The Deterministic6G-V2X project will follow the grant agreement indications on metadata: “Metadata of deposited data must be open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.” As for the specific metadata format, Zenodo utilizes DataCite, a standard fact for describing datasets.

Adequate search keywords will also be provided in the metadata to optimize discoverability and maximize the impact and dissemination of the project data. Through Zenodo, the metadata can be harvested using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name and can also be retrieved through the public REST API. Immediately after publication, metadata is directly searchable in Zenodo’s search engine. Through Zenodo, metadata of each record is also indexed on DataCite servers during DOI registration.

9.4 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

9.4.1 Repository

All data generated by the Deterministic6G-V2X project will be uploaded to Zenodo. Zenodo is a safe and trusted repository built and operated by CERN and OpenAIRE.

No specific arrangements with Zenodo have been explored, as Zenodo is inherently suitable to store the data (datasets, software, deliverables, and publications) generated during the Deterministic6G-V2X project. Nevertheless, the researcher is ready to reconsider the exploration of appropriate arrangements with Zenodo during the project execution based on the project needs. Through Zenodo, all project data will be assigned a DOI.

9.4.2 Data

All datasets and software generated during the Deterministic6G-V2X project will be made publicly available on the Deterministic6G-V2X project Zenodo community [3] and on the project website [1]. Deliverables with a “sensitive” dissemination level (as per the grant agreement) will not be openly released and represent the only exception. Pre-print versions of all scientific publications will be publicly released on the project’s Zenodo community and, optionally, on pre-print servers such as arXiv. Whenever possible and appropriate, scientific publications will be submitted to journals that offer open-access options. All access to zenodo.org will take place through the secure HTTPS protocol.

No restrictions on the use of the project data have been identified. All procedures to ascertain the identity of external users accessing the project data will be delegated to Zenodo, the EU's official repository where all project data will be publicly released.

The project has not identified the need for a data access committee to evaluate or approve access requests to personal or sensitive data.

9.4.3 Metadata

As indicated in the grant agreement, the metadata will be made openly available and licensed under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or an equivalent license. The metadata will contain all the information needed to enable external users to easily find, access, and re-use the project data. According to the Zenodo website, the project data will remain available and findable for 20 years. A copy of the metadata will also be uploaded to the project website. The project website is hosted on GitHub and will remain online after the project ends, providing permanent access to all project data. No specific software documentation or proprietary tools will be required to access or read the data generated by the project.

9.5 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

The data generated during the project (datasets and software) will be formatted and published following a metadata-driven approach and employing standardized formats. The open release of the project data will be accompanied by descriptive metadata that facilitates data understanding, exchange, and re-use across different disciplines. Whenever possible, the generated data will be formatted using open-source and widely accepted machine-readable formats to ensure that the data is easily accessible and exchangeable across different systems.

Whenever possible and appropriate, the documentation of the project data will include references to other existing datasets and software. When needed and feasible, the metadata in Zenodo will reference datasets and data from other projects.

9.6 INCREASE DATA RE-USE

Whenever possible, the project data (datasets, software, publications) will be accompanied by extensive documentation. Documentation will be uploaded to the project's Zenodo community and referenced by the corresponding data. Documentation will allow external users to easily understand the organization and content of the released datasets and to effectively re-use the released software. In the case of publications, documentation will include a detailed description of the design choices, simulation assumptions and scenarios, employed tools, software, and datasets to guarantee the reproducibility of the obtained results.

The project data will be made freely available as soon as possible to permit the widest re-use and will be licensed following the indications set out in the grant agreement. Project data will be licensed "under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License

(CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or a license with equivalent rights, following the principle ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary.’”

The project data will be usable by third parties after the end of the project according to the rules specified by the adopted license. Provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented by the researcher using appropriate standards and described as part of the released data documentation. The goal is to make the project’s results and data as reproducible and reusable as possible.

The researcher is committed to adopting all best practices and scientific methodologies to maximize the quality of the project data. The quality of the datasets and software generated during the project will also be internally validated by the supervisor. All deliverables and publications generated by the researcher during the project will be reviewed by the supervisor prior to their publication on Zenodo to ensure the highest quality level of the project outputs.

10 OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

The data generated by the Deterministic6G-V2X project also includes software and models (see Table 8.1). Both software and models will be managed and shared in line with the same FAIR principles adopted for the publication of other project data types. Software and models will be released on the project’s Zenodo community and, optionally, on GitHub. Through Zenodo, software and models will be assigned a DOI (Findability). The open release of software and models will be protected under a CC BY license (Reusability) and will be accompanied by exhaustive documentation to facilitate their re-use across different systems and disciplines (Interoperability).

11 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

The project does not foresee any direct or indirect costs to align the project’s data management practices with the FAIR principles. All project data will be uploaded to the project’s Zenodo community, which offers a free and unlimited subscription plan. The only exception may be represented by the payment of open-access fees, which are typically required by high-impact journals to openly publish submitted papers. In case any of the project’s publications require the payment of open-access fees, these costs will be covered using part of the project budget (budget category B).

The researcher (Dr. Keyvan Aghababaiyan) will be responsible for data management. Whenever needed, the researcher will rely on the support of the supervisor (Prof. Javier Gozálvez) and the host institution (UMH).

Long-term preservation of the research outputs (data and publications) will be guaranteed by Zenodo. Zenodo guarantees a 20-year lifetime for the project data (software and datasets) and for the pre-print open-access copies of the project publications. No additional resources or costs are required or expected to guarantee the long-term preservation of the project data.

12 DATA SECURITY

The researcher will adopt all the data security standards implemented by the host institution (UMH) and will follow the host institution’s information security guidelines. These guidelines include procedures for backup and restore, as well as measures to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and

accessibility of the project data. With the support of the host institution's IT office, the researcher will maintain an updated local backup copy of the project data on the host institution's servers. The host institution's IT infrastructure also provides secure data transfer through encryption protocols and data encryption techniques.

Data will be published and stored in Zenodo, the EU official repository. Zenodo is a trusted and secure repository that guarantees long-term preservation and curation of the published data (up to 20 years).

13 ETHICS

The researcher does not foresee any ethics or legal issues that could impact data sharing. The Deterministic6G-V2X project plans to exclusively use digital data obtained through simulations, and the use of personal data is not foreseen during the project execution.

The AI-based solutions that will be implemented during the project will not directly impact vehicle driving; for this reason, the project does not foresee any ethical issues regarding the proposed AI-based solutions. The proposed AI-based solutions cannot stigmatize or discriminate against people, do not replace, or influence human decision-making processes, and do not have the potential to lead to negative social behaviors or effects.

14 OTHER ISSUES

The researcher does not foresee the use of other national, funder, sectorial, or departmental procedures for data management. All data management procedures that will be implemented during the Deterministic6G-V2X project are described in this deliverable.

15 REFERENCES

- [1] Deterministic6G-V2X project website: <https://keyvanaghababaiyan.github.io/Deterministic6G-V2X/>
- [2] DMP official EU template: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx
- [3] Deterministic6G-V2X project Zenodo community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/deterministic-6g-v2x/records>

